

SURFACE STUDY OF CERIUM OXIDE BASED COATINGS OBTAINED BY CATHODIC ELECTRODEPOSITION ON ZINC

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ABSTRACT

A surface study of electrodeposited cerium oxide based coatings is presented. Different surface analytical techniques were used in order to obtain complementary information to fully characterize such complex systems. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy was used as the main technique to determine the surface composition of the coating. The analysis of the core level peaks of the elements provides additional information about the functional groups present on the surface. A mixture of Ce (III) and Ce (IV) was found in the coating and their proportion was calculated at different depths. The analysis of the O 1s core level peak revealed a triple structure whose origin will be discussed. To support the results obtained, electron stimulated desorption was performed. The study was completed with Auger electron spectroscopy and Raman spectroscopy, both techniques having different surface sensitivities. From all these results, it is derived that incomplete electrochemical reactions occurred during the growth of the coatings. This led to rather complex compositions, in which defective cerium oxides are the major species. In addition, hydroxides, carbonates and nitrates are also present, together with adsorbed water.

Keywords: Cerium oxides ;XPS; ESD; AES

INTRODUCTION

Rare earth elements and in particular cerium oxide coatings have been subject of extensive study during the last years as an environmentally friendly alternative to chromium conversion coatings to protect materials against corrosion [1,2]. These coatings have been previously applied on different substrates such as aluminium [3–5] or steel [6,7] by electrodeposition methods, where the final characteristics of the cerium coating are highly dependent on the experimental conditions employed for their elaboration (solution, concentration, pH, applied current, . . .). In essence, these coatings presented a mixture of Ce (III) and Ce (IV) [6], mainly in the form of oxides and hydroxides [3,7]. However, the precise nature and location of the species are not well understood despite this is of major importance for the final anticorrosion properties conferred by these coatings, as well as their hydrophobic characteristics.

Therefore, in this work a comprehensive surface study was performed on cerium oxide based coatings electrodeposited on zinc from a nitrate bath. Different surface analytical techniques were used in order to obtain complementary information to fully characterize such complex system. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) was used as the main characterization technique to determine the surface chemistry. Using this technique the proportion of cerium in each oxidation state was calculated on the surface and compared with inner parts of the coating. In addition, a triple structure of the O 1s core level peak was analysed, where the presence of water seems to be very important for the final characteristics of the coating. Water contact angle measurements allowed to study the evolution of this specie on the coatings before and after sputtering. Complementary analytical techniques with different surface sensitivities (Raman spectroscopy and Auger

electron spectroscopy) were also employed to obtain global information at different depths of the coating. Finally, electron stimulated desorption (ESD) experiments will be presented for the first time in these systems.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

1 cm x 1 cm coupons of pure Zn (99.999%) were mechanically polished and finally etched in sonicated 10 vol% Nital for 30 s immediately before the electrodeposition process in a 3 electrode cell [8,9]. The electrolytic bath was composed of a 0.1 M Ce(NO₃)₃ 6H₂O aqueous solution and a current density of -1.5 mA cm⁻² was applied for 20 min. The bath was not agitated during electrodeposition. After electrodeposition, the sample was thoroughly rinsed in ethanol and dried in a desiccator overnight before any further subsequent analysis.

The Raman spectra were recorded with a Jobin Yvon LabRam HR8000 spectrometer equipped with a confocal microscope using an incident beam of 632.82 nm emitted by a HeNe laser.

The XPS measurements were performed in an ultra high- vacuum (UHV) chamber with a base pressure of 1×10^{-10} mbar. The angle between the hemispherical analyzer (Specs-PHOIBOS100) and the plane of the surface was kept at 60° and the X-ray radiation was the Mg K α line (1253.6 eV). The survey spectra were recorded with a pass energy of 40 eV and an energy step of 0.25 eV. Narrow scans of Ce 3d and O 1s core levels were recorded using a pass energy of 15 eV with a energy step of 0.1 eV. The binding energy (BE) scale was calibrated with respect to the C 1s at 285 eV. The analysis of the XPS results was carried out with the Casa XPS software, using Gaussian with 20% Lorentzian for the fitting procedure. Before XPS data were analysed, the contribution of Mg K α satellite lines was subtracted and the background removed by a Shirley routine. Ion sputtering was performed by Ar⁺ sputtering at 1.4 keV over an area of 6 mm 10 mm and a total current of 0.3 μ A, which was chosen to minimize any phenomenon of preferential sputtering of light elements (e.g. oxygen). The erosion rate under these conditions was estimated to 0.12 A° / μ A min.

Contact angle (CA) measurements were carried out by the sessile drop method using water drops of 4 μ l at room temperature. The surface energy evaluation system (SEE) [10] was used for the acquisition of the drop images and their analysis.

Electron stimulated desorption (ESD) and Auger electron spectroscopy (AES) analysis of the cerium coating were performed in a different UHV system with a residual pressure of 8×10^{-10} mbar equipped with a quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS), a double pass cylindrical mirror analyser (CMA) and a low energy electron gun. The CMA was operated in the N(E) mode at 3 keV and then the spectra were derived. The electron current of the sample was 100 nA (3×10^{-3} A/cm²) to minimize electron damage of the surface species. ESD experiments were performed with the axis of the low energy, high electron current gun was placed at $45^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ with respect to the sample normal and the energy of the impinging electrons could be varied from 5 to 600 eV. The electron current was nearly constant in the energy range from 50 to 600 eV but varied for energies lower than 50 eV. Thus, surface ion currents from the sample were normalized to a constant electron current density according to the form of the electron current versus energy. The QMS and the CMA are placed in the same axis, so ESD and AES experiments could be performed by rotating the sample 180°. The sensitivity factors used for the quantification of the AES spectra are 0.338 for O, 0.061 for Ce and 0.165 for C.

1. Results and discussion

After electrodeposition of the cerium oxide based coatings on zinc, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations in the cross- section configuration (Fig. 1) revealed a quite opened morphology all across the coating thickness, with a needle-like microstructure. For a comprehensive study the surface chemistry of the coatings, different analytical techniques with different surface sensitivities were employed to obtain a global overview of the coating composition.

Fig. 2 presents the Raman spectra of the coatings. The main peak at around 456 cm^{-1} corresponds to the F2g Ce–O vibration mode associated with CeO_2 [11]. The asymmetry of this peak with a shoulder at higher wave numbers (480 cm^{-1}) could be either caused by the particle size, the oxygen vacancies or the incorporation of foreign ions [12,13]. However, the vibration band at around 600 cm^{-1} supports the presence of an oxygen-defective cerium oxide [11,13] and, thus identify the likely reason for the shoulder at 480 cm^{-1} . The vibration bands at 714 , and 1078 cm^{-1} are ascribed to carbonate species [14], while the peaks at 740 and 1050 cm^{-1} are quoted in the literature as free nitrates [15]. The presence of carbonates is very common in ceria based materials, due to adsorption of atmospheric carbon dioxide [16,17]. The open morphology of the coating (Fig. 1) favours this CO_2 adsorption and, thus, explains the presence of these compounds in the system. On the other hand, part of the nitrates from the electrolyte can be trapped in the coating due to the fast formation of the films. Therefore, according to the Raman spectra, these cerium electrodeposited coatings are mainly composed of defective cerium oxide, with incorporation of carbonates and nitrates.

Fig. 1. Cross section of the cerium oxide coating.

Fig. 2. Raman spectra of the cerium coating.

In order to better understand the composition and chemical state of the elements in the cerium coatings, XPS was used to analyse the coatings. Ce, O, C and N were found in the analysis, but no signal of Zn was detected in the coatings. Oxygen and carbon were the major species present on the surface, probably due to the atmospheric contaminants or as remnants after the coating formation. The thickness of the coating

(around 5 μm) hindered Zn detection from the substrate. Table 1 presents the composition (at%) extracted from the analysis of the wide energy range scan carried out on the surface as well as after short Ar^+ bombardment to remove the surface contamination. For easier comparison O/Ce and C/Ce ratios are also included in the table. The O/Ce and C/Ce ratios of the as-received sample were 11 and 19, respectively. After sputtering, a significant removal of contaminants occurred and the proportion of cerium significantly increased, leading to O/Ce and C/Ce ratios close to 4 and 3, respectively. Further detailed analysis of the core level spectra of each element was performed to analyse the chemical nature of the species present. The analysis of the N 1s peak (not shown) put in evidence that most of the nitrogen at the top surface was present as NO_3^- (407.2 eV). However, after sputtering partial nitrate reduction occurred. This reduction could be caused by the Ar^+ bombardment. Nevertheless, the nitrates from the electrolytic bath can be also reduced upon the electrodeposition process as also described in [11]:

Table 1. Composition (at%) of the sample.

Composition (at%)	Composition (at%)			Ratio	
	C	Ce N	O	O/C	C/Ce
Surface	56	3.7	34	11	18.7
Sputtered	37	12.4	47	3.9	3.1

Fig. 3 shows the normalized XPS spectra of Ce, C and O core levels for the as received and the argon ion cleaned samples. Fig. 3a presents the analysis of the Ce 3d core level spectra. Details of the analysis procedure are given elsewhere [18]. The shadowed components (blue) corresponded to Ce (III) and the empty ones (red) to Ce (IV). From deconvolution of the spectra, it was observed that both Ce (IV) and Ce (III) species are present on the coating. The quantification reflected that Ce (IV) is predominant on the top surface (58%). After the sputtering process, the Ce (III) content increased by 5%. On the one hand, this small variation could be explained by a reduction of Ce (IV) species into Ce (III) caused by Ar^+ bombardment [3,19]. However, the coexistence of both oxidation states before sputtering indicates the incorporation of variable amounts of Ce (III) within the coating. This is supported by the presence of carbonates in form of $\text{Ce}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3$ [20]. Indeed, an analysis of the C 1s core level spectra (Fig. 3b), confirmed the presence of carbon species even after sputtering, probably due to the porous nature of the coating that impeded the complete removal of contaminants. The component around 289 eV confirmed the presence of carbonate species [21,22], which is doubled after the sputtering process and, therefore, confirms that carbonate species are present in larger amounts inside the cerium coating, as previously observed by Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 2). This evolution is related to the larger amount of Ce (III) registered after sputtering.

Fig. 3c presents the curve fitting of O 1s core level. The shape of the peak justifies the presence of at least three components. The first component, named O1, that appeared at lower BE (529.6 ± 0.2 eV), corresponds to lattice oxygen in oxide form from the cerium oxide coating [1,19,23–26]. The second component at 531.6 ± 0.2 eV, named O2, has been attributed in the literature either to hydroxyl species [1,24–27] or adsorbed oxygen species [27,28], defective oxides [25], or carbonates species [20]. Finally, the third component at higher BE (532.9 ± 0.1 eV), named O3, can be associated with molecular water [1,26] and to the presence of nitrites and nitrates [29] previously mentioned.

The analysis of the O 1s core level evidenced that the O2 component is the main contribution on the outer part of the cerium coating (43%), where there is also a significant amount of adsorbed water (23% O3). Upon

sputtering, the proportion of O2 and O3 components decreased and the oxide species of O1 became predominant (56%), hence, suggesting that the inner part of the coating is mainly composed of cerium oxides. Concerning the species contributing to the O2 component, different explanations can be considered taking into account the electrochemical process and the porous structure of the coating. The acicular morphology of the coating observed by SEM (Fig. 1), confirmed the existence of hydroxides [30]. In addition, the presence of carbonates and defective oxides has been already observed by Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 2). Therefore, these analyses put in evidence a rather complex nature of the coating grown by electrodeposition in the conditions used in this work, where the O2 component is formed by a partial contribution of hydroxides, defective oxides and carbonates. Hamlaoui et al. [11] previously described in detail the steps for the formation of CeO₂ from nitrate baths. Hydroxides are reaction intermediates for the formation of CeO₂ by dehydration reactions (Eqs. (3) and (4)) [11]:

Therefore, the presence of these species suggests incomplete reactions during the growth process. The oxides formed are oxygen defective according to Raman analysis (Fig. 2). The overall positive charge of such defective oxides allows water to be bounded to the structure as reported on similar systems by differential scanning calorimetry [11,31]. In addition, water is present as reactant or product in most reactions described in [11] to form CeO₂. The incomplete reactions to form the cerium oxide coating reported here not only leads to the presence of hydroxides, but could also explain the presence of water (O3 component) even after sputtering of the surface as the open morphology of the coating (Fig. 1) facilitates the incorporation of water into the system. Furthermore, the existence of a hydrated cerium oxide inside the film cannot be ruled out [31,32].

Fig. 3. Normalised (a) Ce 3d, (b) C 1s and (c) O 1s XPS core level spectra of the surface (top) and after sputtering to remove 1 nm of material.

In summary, these coatings are rather complex. They are mainly composed of cerium defective oxide, but the XPS measurements also confirmed the presence of hydroxides, carbonates, water and nitrates consequence of

incomplete reactions during the growth process.

In order to evaluate the presence of water and its variation after sputtering, water contact angle measurements were carried out on the samples. Fig. 4 presents a comparison of two water droplets of 4 μl on the cerium oxide coating before and after Ar^+ bombardment. It can be clearly observed that Ar^+ bombardment produces an increase in the contact angle from 94° to 134° , making the cerium oxide coating more hydrophobic. It is well known that the contact angle depends on the surface roughness as well as the surface chemistry. Following the Wenzel model [33], Bhushan and Jung [34] described how for rough solid surfaces, a hydrophobic surface ($\theta > 90^\circ$) becomes more hydrophobic with an increase in the roughness. It is well known that sputtering reduces the surface roughness, and so a less hydrophobic surface should be expected in these cerium oxide coatings. However, the opposite was observed and, thus, the surface chemistry of the coating appears to play a key role on its wettability. Water contact angle can be used as a simple method to determine modifications on the polarity of surfaces [35]. In this case, the increase observed in the water CA after sputtering clearly puts in evidence a reduction in the amount of polar groups. The XPS analysis revealed that the main polar groups present on the surface were hydroxides and water (Fig. 3c) and confirmed that both components decreased after sputtering, but especially water. Therefore, it seems that sputtering of the surface generated a depleted region in which the amount of water is severely reduced, causing an increase of the hydrophobicity of the coating.

After the XPS experiments, the sample was extracted from the UHV chamber and exposed to atmosphere for three months. After this period the sample was introduced to the AES chamber to make new analysis. The peaks observed in the AES spectra of Fig. 5 were identified as Ce(NVV), Ce(MNN), C(KLL) and O(KLL) transitions that led to a surface composition of 56% Ce, 27% O and 17% C (at%). The C/Ce (≈ 0.3) and O/Ce (≈ 0.5) ratios were lower than those obtained from the XPS measurements after sputtering. It seemed that the surface of the cerium coating became less reactive after the XPS experiments, and a little atmospheric contamination uptake took place. Note also that the O/Ce ratio of 0.5 corresponds to a defective Ce oxide on the top surface, which implied that oxidation of Ce (III) did not occur. In contrast with the XPS measurements, nitrogen was not detected by AES. This could be explained in terms of the loss of the weakly bounded nitrates (free nitrates) at the top surface of the sample upon Ar^+ sputtering on the previous XPS measurements. However, taking into account the higher penetration depth of the XPS in comparison with AES, this could also imply an inner location of nitrogen inside the cerium oxide coating.

Fig. 5. AES spectrum of the Ce electrodeposited sample.

Fig. 4. Water contact angle on cerium coating (a) before and (b) after Ar^+ bombardment.

Fig. 6. ESD H^+ yield as a function of the electron energy (a) after atmospheric exposure, (b) after electron bombardment (4 h, 5×10^{-6} A/cm², 600 eV), (c) after 24 h and (d) after an electron bombardment like (b).

After the AES measurements, ESD experiments were carried out in different conditions as an attempt to confirm the species found on the analysis of the O 1s XPS core level. In these experiments, H^+ was the only ion detected. Fig. 6 presents the ion yield of H^+ as a function of the electron incident energy at different conditions. After atmospheric exposure (Fig. 6a), two thresholds of electron energy can be observed, one at 30 eV and the other at 220 eV. Following the Feibelman–Knotek model [36], the first threshold was assigned to H^+ ejection as a consequence of the AES electronic transitions by primary excitation of the O 2s. The increase of the slope observed at about 40 eV could be assigned to the excitation of the Ce 5s. In addition, the maximum at 130 eV can be justified on the grounds of the maximum of the Ce 5s + O 2s electronic excitation transitions, at about 3×30 eV and 3×40 eV. The second threshold at 220 eV could be identified by excitation of the Ce 4p (223–206 eV). However, the maxima appeared at 360 and 490 eV instead of having maximum yields at 669–618 eV, so the H^+ cannot be related to the excitation of the Ce 4p. Instead, it is proposed that the secondary electrons produced in sub layer atoms could be the origin of this threshold, as the ejected electrons are able to ionise the O 2s and the Ce 5s of the outer atoms.

The second condition studied corresponded to the surface (Fig. 6a) after subject to electron bombardment during 4 h, 5×10^{-6} A/cm² at 600 eV incident electron energy (Fig. 6b). The most significant result is the lowering of the H^+ intensity in the whole electron energy range in comparison to the previous condition (Fig. 6a), but mainly at incident electron energies higher than 200 eV. After this measurement, the electron current was turned off for 24 h and then a threshold experiment was performed (Fig. 6c). It is interesting to notice that the H^+ yield does not recover the values of the

beginning (Fig. 6a). This means that re-adsorption of H from the residual vacuum, which mainly consist of H_2 and H_2O , is very low. In order to analyse this effect in detail, additional adsorption experiments in D_2O atmosphere (30 Langmuir) were performed so as to detect deuterium during desorption. Using D_2O instead of H_2O it is possible to distinguish between species adsorbed from the atmosphere or from the residual vacuum. However, neither D^+ , nor D_2O^+ or DO^+ was detected on the surface with the sensitivity limit of our instrumentation. Therefore, even though the samples were exposed for three months to the atmosphere after sputtering, the dehydration produced seems to be permanent, hindering the D_2O adsorption on the surface. This implies that after Ar^+ bombardment (Fig. 4), the hydrophobicity of these coatings can be maintained in the long term. Finally, 4 h of additional electron bombardment equivalent to the conditions presented in Fig. 6b were performed (Fig. 6d). It can be observed that the H^+ at high energy has disappeared and the decrease of the intensity of the first peak continues.

Fig. 7. IED spectra for different energies of the incident electrons for H^+ desorbed ions.

Fig. 7 presents the ion kinetic energy distribution (IED) of the EDS H^+ desorbed ions measured with three different incident energies (150, 300 and 600 eV). Two most probable kinetic energies were found: 2.3 eV and 3.6 eV. The distribution obtained seems to be irrespective of the electron incident energy, even though the intensity obtained varied with it. This result implies that H^+ was desorbed by the same electronic process in all conditions tested.

From the ESD experiments can be derived that the determined thresholds at 30 eV and 40 eV of electron energy (Fig. 6), corresponded to the O 2s and Ce 5s electronic

excitations. These results are in accordance with the two Gaussian distribution found in the IED spectra (Fig. 7) and, thus, the most probable bonds of the desorbed species are: Ce–H and Ce–O–H.

CONCLUSIONS

Electrodeposited cerium-oxide based coatings on Zn substrates were investigated by complementary surface analytical techniques. Comprehensive information on the chemical nature of these coatings was derived. First, the needle-like microstructure leaves quite opened areas that result in a rather complex composition. In general, the coatings are mainly composed of defective cerium oxide. Both Ce (III) and Ce (IV) species are present in the coating, with a larger proportion of Ce (IV) at the top surface. Other species were also found: the hydroxides detected by XPS and confirmed by ESD are consequence of incomplete reactions to form oxides (Eqs. (3) and (4)), mainly in the outermost areas of the coating. Carbonates and nitrites were found by Raman and XPS. The first one is mainly present in inner parts of the coating and its presence could be related to CO₂ adsorption, consequence of the open morphology of the coating. On the other hand, the presence of nitrates is consequence of a fast grow process, where these species got trapped during the electrodeposition process. Finally, the presence of water can be ascribed to the porous nature of the coating, which favours this kind of adsorption. We have presented for first time a preliminary study of the ESD of cerium oxide based coatings on Zn surface, where H⁺ is the only detected ion desorbed. The excitation of the Ce 5s and O 2s core levels is the origin of the subsequent AES transitions yielding the H⁺ to the vacuum. According to the threshold and ion energy distribution we propose the Ce–O–H and Ce–H species are responsible for this desorption. The origin of the O and H species should come from the cerium coating preparation process by electrolysis.

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